

Correction to: Can a Good Person be a Good Trader? An Ethical Defense of Financial Trading

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The article Can a Good Person be a Good Trader? An Ethical Defense of Financial Trading, written by Marta Rocchi and David Thunder, was originally published Online First without Open Access. After publication in volume 159, issue 1, page 89–103 the authors decided to opt for Open Choice and to make the article an Open Access publication. Therefore, the copyright of the article has been changed to © The Authors 2017 and the article is forthwith distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link

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